

Prof. D.Sc.

Department: Marketing and Strategic Planning, Faculty of Management and Administration, UNWE, Bulgaria

Corresponding author/-s:

e-mail: s.jelev@unwe.bg

ORCID:

DOI:

Published First Online:

Pages: 13-17

How to cite:

IS THERE A “100% LOYALTY PRONENESS” ON A HOUSEHOLD LEVEL?

ABSTRACT

In 1956 Cunningham, an American market researcher, presents the hypothesis that there is a so-called loyalty proneness. The thesis states that some consumers are to be prone to be, at the same time loyal to several different product categories. To evaluate this hypothesis Cunningham bases his research on panel data that comes from the consumer panel of the Chicago Tribune newspaper, and he uses the SCR metric. In this article two more hypotheses based on the Cunningham's “loyalty proneness” are introduced, and evaluated, both of them being a modification on his hypothesis. The first hypothesis states that some 100% loyal households can be prone to be 100% loyal to several product categories at the same time, within a specified time limit. The second hypothesis states that in some 100% loyal households there is a proneness to be 100% loyal in one product category, for two or more consecutive years. Based on the data from GFK Bulgaria's Consumer Scan household panel, for six product categories and for four consecutive years on the Bulgarian market, both hypotheses are confirmed.

KEY WORDS

Customer loyalty, 100% customer loyalty, loyalty proneness, synchronic loyalty proneness, diachronic loyalty proneness

JEL

D11, D12, M31

INTRODUCTION

In 1956 Cunningham (Cunningham, 1956), an American market researcher, presents the hypothesis that there is a so-called loyalty proneness. The hypothesis states that some consumers are to be prone to be, at the same time loyal to several different product categories. To evaluate this hypothesis Cunningham bases his research on panel data that comes from the consumer panel of the Chicago Tribune newspaper, and he uses the SCR measure (share of category requirements), which he introduces in the sphere of loyalty market research. To be more precise, Cunningham uses the average SCR (the average of the SCR values of all the brands purchased), while one can also use the maximum SCR (i.e. the SCR of the most purchased brand). In his calculations Cunningham takes out the products purchased on a promotion/discount, and he finds there is a low correlation of $r=0.3$. In 1995 East (East, Harris, Willson, & Lomax, 1995) finds a modest correlation of $r=0.46$, while researching four different categories of consumer products. In 2008 East, Wright and Vahnel (East,

Singh , Wright, & Vanhuele, 2008) find that if the products purchased on a promotion/discount weren't taken out of the data, the correlation coefficient values would have been much higher. They claim: "It seems likely that it is the attraction of the deal that often draws people away from their usual brand and that deal proneness should not be excluded".

In the research program "100% loyalty, 100% loyal", which was done between 2014 and 2017, a couple of modifications on Cunninghams hypothesis were introduced and tested on a specific consumer group – the 100% loyal household one. 100% loyal households are those, which in a specified period of time (usually a year) purchase only from one brand from a product category.

The first modification to Cunninghams hypothesis is that: some "100% loyal households" can be prone to be "100% loyal" in several product categories at the same time, within a specified time limit. This proneness for 100% loyalty we call proneness for a synchronised 100% loyalty, because it is based on a simultaneous 100% loyalty to two or more product categories within the same period of time. For example, when a household, in 2012, was 100% loyal in the category of margarine, coffee and washing detergents, it is prone to be in the proneness for a synchronised 100% loyalty group of consumers.

The second modification to Cunninghams thesis is that: in some "100% loyal" households there is a proneness to be "100% loyal" in one product category, for two or more consecutive years. This proneness for 100% loyalty we call proneness for a diachronic 100% loyalty, because there is a 100% loyalty to a single product category for two or more consecutive years. For example, when a household, was 100% loyal in the category of margarine in 2010, 2011 and 2012, it is prone to be in the proneness for a diachronic category.

DATA

1. Empirical Data Source

The data on which the "100% loyalty, 100% loyal" research program is based on is the result from GFK Bulgaria's Consumer Scan Panel, which surveys household spending on fast moving consumer goods in Bulgaria. The data gathering method used is fulfilling of a diary the person responsible for the household purchases. Every month two diaries are used to write in the purchases – one for every two weeks. This is done so as to control the quality of data collection (regularity of the fulfilment of the diary). The sample is multistage cluster sample. In each of the years the survey was done the size of the sample varies from 2000 to 2500 households. In one of the households there is a limited number of product categories, so as to limit the load of the person responsible for the fulfilling of the diaries, and thus increase the quality of the data stemming from this reduced load. All the recordings in the diaries include numerical values – kilograms, liters, quantity of purchased goods, as well as the prices of the aforementioned goods.

2. Product Category Selection

The product categories of frankfurters, margarine, toothpaste, washing detergents, beer and coffee, were subject to the analysis performed in the "100% loyalty, 100% loyal" research program The survey period used is from the following years – 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012. In the selection of the six product categories an important factor was for each them to differ immensely from the next, so as to be able to get the highest level of generalization of conclusions by using MSoD approach (Many sets of data). What is different in each of the product categories?

- Some are purchased mostly in the household (washing detergents, toothpaste, margarine), some are purchased externally (beer, coffee, etc.).
- Some are purchased by more than one member of the household (beer, toothpaste), others mostly by the housewife (washing detergent).
- Some have a more expressed individual consumption within the family (beer, toothpaste), others have a more expressed collective consumption (coffee, washing detergent).

- In some categories within a single purchase a single quantity of that product category is purchased (washing detergent, margarine), in others it's multiple of the same product (beer, frankfurters).
- Some categories have no consumption away from the household (washing detergent), some have a limited consumption (frankfurters in a hot dog, margarine in a sandwich), others can be consumed both within the household, and away from it (beer).
- Some categories have a more expressed individual preference (beer, coffee), others have a lesser one (washing detergent, margarine) – and more often than not the decision for the selection is done by the housewife.
- Some categories have predominantly Bulgarian brands (frankfurters, beer), some have International ones (coffee, toothpaste), and others have a mixture of Bulgarian and International ones (washing detergents).
- Some categories are more innovative (washing detergents, toothpaste), others are more traditional (frankfurters, coffee).
- The categories have a different frequency of purchases and consumption associated with them.
- Some categories have a strong expressed seasonality of consumption (beer), others have less (coffee).

3. Is there proneness for a synchronic 100% loyalty?

In table 1 of the attached data the 100% loyal household are filtered by number of categories and by years. This way when the first row of data is read, one can see that the 100% loyal households in a single product category, of the six surveyed in 2009, were 41.5% of the households, for 2010 their share was 42.2%, and so on, and the average for the four years for 100% loyal households in a single product category in the survey is 44.6%. The second row of data shows the households loyal in two product categories. For 2009 their share was 34.7%, in 2010 it was 35.1%, and so on, and the average for the four years in 100% loyal households in two product categories in the survey is 33.9%. The last row shows the average for the number of categories 100% loyal households are loyal to.

Table 1 Distribution of 100% loyal households, by number of categories, to which they were loyal to, for each year (in %)

Type of household	Year				Average
	2009	2010	2011	2012	
100% loyal in 1 category	41,5	42,2	46,7	48,1	44,6
100% loyal in 2 categories	34,7	35,1	33,9	32,0	33,9
100% loyal in 3 categories	17,8	17,0	15,0	15,4	16,3
100% loyal in 4 categories	5,1	5,4	3,2	3,9	4,4
100% loyal in 5 categories	0,8	0,4	1,0	0,5	0,7
100% loyal in 6 categories	0,1	0	0,1	0,1	0,1
Average of 100% loyal to ... (number) of categories	1,89	1,87	1,78	1,77	1,83

Two facts partially confirm the modifications on Cunningham's hypothesis for the proneness for a synchronic 100% loyalty. First, the average loyalty to two product categories, out of the six surveyed, i.e. 100% loyal households are loyal to two product categories at the same time (the last row of data) Second, the share of 100% loyal households in two or more categories is an average of 55.4% (last column $33.9 + 16.3 + 4.4 + 0.7 + 0.1 = 55.4$); the share of 100% loyal households in three or more product categories is an average of 21.5% (last column $16.3 + 4.4 + 0.7 + 0.1 = 21.5$), and so on. When I write partially confirmed, I am referring to two things. First, with each year some households leave the strata of 100% loyal households, only to be replaced by other households incoming into it. Based on that, one can talk about a kind of a *situative synchronic loyalty*: households which in the

surveyed time limit are 100% loyal to one product category, could also be loyal to other product categories at the same time. Second, it is possible that the selection of the product categories is a factor for the confirmation or the rejection of the hypothesis, which could be a source for a further research on the subject.

One more thing to note, as an interesting fact, is that the share of 100% loyal households for two or more product categories is steadily declining in the years: in 2009 it was 58.5%, for 2010 57.8%, for 2011 53.3%, and for 2012 r. 51.9%. If that is a pattern (regularity) or happenstance could be measured/evaluated, in the future, by a longer term survey.

4. Is there proneness for a diachronic 100% loyalty?

Do 100% loyal households remain the same in the years? Or is there a proneness for a diachronic 100% loyalty?

From other data stemming from the research program it was found that the market, as an institution, reproduces the share of 100% loyal households, to the surveyed product categories and time limits, in a relatively stable manner. But it was also found that “older” 100% loyal households, are replaced with “new” 100% loyal households. Stated more simply, the occurrence of 100% loyal household is stable in time and product categories, however, its bearers, the 100% loyal households, are different with time and with product categories.

To evaluate the modified hypothesis for proneness for a disynchronised 100% loyalty, out of the whole sample, one can only work with the data subset from the panel that has remained the same for the whole period of the survey, the four years and the six product categories, i.e. those households who have fulfilled their diaries for the entirety of the survey and for each of the product categories. The data shown in table 2 is calculated based on the aforementioned data subset.

Another thing must be noted before we can go ahead and look at the data. One mustn't forget that level on which the data is measured here is on a product category, not on a brand level, and the specific brands in it. That doesn't mean that when one notices that household X was 100% loyal to a product category, for example for frankfurters in 2009, 2010 and 2011, it was loyal to a single brand. Different combinations are possible: every year the household was 100% loyal to different brands; every year it was 100% loyal to the same brand; the first year the household was loyal to one brand, the next year to another one, the third year it returned to the brand from the first year, etc.

Table 2 Distribution of shares for 100% loyal households by number of years and product categories (in %)

Number of years of 100% loyalty	Frankfurters	Margarine	Toothpaste	Washing detergent	Beer	Coffee	Average
1 year	55,9	45,9	53,3	52,9	54,9	42,6	50,9
2 years	31,6	26,9	28,4	31,7	32,9	27	29,8
3 years	11,1	18,2	15,7	11,8	11	20,6	14,7
4 years	1,4	9	2,7	3,6	1,2	9,8	4,6

The data from table 2 shows the distribution of the 100% loyal households by years and by product categories. It can be discerned that out of all the 100% loyal households in the category of frankfurters for the entire four year period of the survey, 55.9% were 100% loyal only in a single year. The share of 100% loyal households for two years is 31.6%, for three years 11.1%, and for four years – 0.4%. Out of all 100% loyal households for the entire four year period of the survey in the category of margarine, 45.9% were 100% loyal only in a single year, 26.9% in two years, 18.2% in three years, and 9% in four years.

The data also serves as a base for the conclusion that there is a diachronic 100% loyalty, i.e. some households continue to be loyal to the same product category for more than a year. Out of the 100%

loyal households, between 44.1% (for frankfurters) and 57.4% (for coffee) are loyal to the six product categories for more than one year, from the whole four year span of the survey.

Several things should be noted as well:

- There is a discernable difference in the size of the diachronic 100% loyalty within the product categories. The biggest difference is between coffee and margarine, and the smallest is between beer and frankfurters.
- There is defined pattern (regularity) for a “regression of the loyalty”. For each of the product categories the share of the 100% loyal households for a year is sizably larger than the one for two years, which is sizably larger than the one for three years, and so on. When the data is averaged for all product categories the proportion of 51:30:15:5 shows up (see the last column of table 2).

CONCLUSION

In this article two hypothesis were risen to test the so-called loyalty proneness, both of which are modifications of Cunningham’s hypothesis, which stated that in some consumers there is proneness for them to be loyal to several product categories at the same time. The first hypothesis states that for some 100% loyal households there is proneness for them to be 100% loyal simultaneously to several product categories within a specified time limit. This type of proneness for 100% loyalty we call synchronic 100% loyalty, because it refers to a simultaneous 100% loyalty to two or more product categories, within a single period of time. The second hypothesis states that for some 100% loyal households there is proneness for them to be 100% loyal to a single product category for two or more consecutive years. This proneness for 100% loyalty we call diachronic 100% loyalty, because it refers to 100% loyalty to a single product category for two or more consecutive years. Based on the data from GFK Bulgaria’s Consumer Scan consumer panel, for six product categories and for four consecutive years, on the Bulgarian market, both hypothesis is confirmed.

REFERENCES

- Cunningham, R. M. (1956). Brand Loyalty-What, Where, How Much. *Harvard Business Review*, 116-128.
- East, R., Harris, P., Willson, G., & Lomax, W. (1995). Loyalty to supermarkets. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 5(1), 99-109. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09593969500000006>
- East, R., Singh, J., Wright, M., & Vanhuele, M. (2008). *Consumer Behaviour: Applications in Marketing*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.